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Sub-topic: 7.1 PV Economics and Markets.

AMPERE: a new project for innovative heterojunction manufacturing solutions to improve competitiveness of the European PV manufacturing industry.

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Abstract

The European PV manufacturing industry has faced strong foreign competition in the last years, which has led to a dramatic reduction of its production capacity. It has completely shifted from a massive leadership at the beginning of the new millennium, with five EU companies in the top ten manufacturers, to a situation of survival where few of them are struggling in an actual extremely competitive market. Hopefully, Europe still has solid industrial assets consisting of silicon & material suppliers, and high quality equipment suppliers that constitute the core of a value chain to be rebuilt. Innovative manufacturing solutions, that substantially improve and reboot the competitiveness of the European PV sector, are mandatory to win competitiveness worldwide PV market.

AMPERE, acronym for **A**utomated photovoltaic cell and **M**odule industrial **P**roduction to regain and secure **E**uropean **R**enewable **E**nergy market, was born for these purposes. AMPERE project aims to the setting-up of an innovative 100 MWp full-scale automated pilot line in production environment and at the same time to a rapid scale up to 250 MWp paving the way to the GWp scale. The main goal of AMPERE is to develop an innovative European and sustainable manufacturing PV line to produce heterojunction technology (HJT) silicon solar cells and modules; This technology is indeed mature to compete against worldwide mainstream technologies, and already demonstrated its ability to reach high power modules. The project will target on the LCOE reduction of at least 15% compared to conventional PV mc-Si technology. The reduction of the costs will be achieved thanks to the intrinsic innovation in the production of the HJT cells and modules based on new coating and passivation schemes for solar cells and module contacting systems.

The expected impact of AMPERE is a regain of competitiveness in the entire EU PV value chain, from materials, to equipment and cell/module manufacturers to end users energy company. The consortium is composed by a consolidate team of well-established research centers, universities and industrials partners with all the necessary experience in the entire chain of HJT cells and modules development and production line.

Purpose of the work

A race towards lower costs and higher competitiveness in PV sector has led to a readily decrease of module prices over time as the historical PV Learning Curve teaches; Asian manufacturers seem to have regained margins and their overcapacities still represent a risk for price decrease and price stabilization cannot reasonably be expected in the coming years [1]. The EU value chain has not entirely disappeared yet, as European equipment suppliers have temporarily benefited from the strong Asian demand. But on long term basis, due to its large domination in PV manufacturing, Asia will attract and create a large part of the forthcoming PV material and equipment suppliers, thus reducing even more the PV European system. AMPERE will try to tackle this trend and for the purpose it will focus on the industrialization and automation of innovative HJT technologies, based on a well-developed assessed and demonstrated HJT owing to the main partners of the consortium [2], [3], [4]. The project involves a strong industrial and academic partners with a wide value chain represented by European leading industries, from technology providers/developers (NORSUN and MEYER BURGER) to manufacturer (3SUN) and finally to end-user (EGP). The

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main objective of AMPERE is to develop and secure the European supply chain of PV manufacturing by implementing a large scale cell and module industrial pilot lines. The implementation of innovative technologies into these industrial manufacturing lines will demonstrate that a larger production of PV products at a competitive COO and subsequent LCOE compared to non-European manufacturer is possible.

AMPERE main technology is focused on the demonstration of feasibility of bi-facial cells and modules based on heterojunction technology (HJT) at a 100 MWp industrial pilot line. It should lead to a short-scale upgrade at 250 MWp and then show the path to the GWp-scale which will arise fairly quickly after the end of AMPERE: the project will deliver the roadmap to reach production capacity stated. The project will be focused on the improved PV module power, reliability and durability to reduce the cost needed to fix and maintain PV plant and decrease its operational risks. The metric will be applied on the existing PV module industrial production site of 3SUN in Catania, Italy[4].

The project aims to assure the full value chain sustainability in Europe. The sustainability assessment will consider how extended life and improved efficiency will improve known upstream and downstream issues and the results can inform future PV design aspects and criteria

Approach and objectives.

AMPERE will start from existing technologies that have been demonstrated during previous European successful projects. Cells technological platform of CEA-INES (TRL6) and Module technological platform of MBR (TRL6) will be the first two bricks of the project where a technology selection process will enable the implementation of the best materials and instruments into the existing industrial production line of 3SUN (TRL 7-8), which will work as demonstration bed. By establishing a cell and module industrial production line of 100 MWp representative of the large scale production, AMPERE will trigger new activities in the European PV value chain and revitalize this sector. **It is expected that with HJT bifacial modules the LCOE will be reduced of at least 15% compared to the main technologies on the market in most of the geographical areas of interest [5].**

The recent trend shows a continuous decrease of module prices which have reached <0,5 €/Wp for premium market modules and < 0.36 €/Wp for mainstream. [1]. AMPERE project promise to be competitive with the Premium Market consisting of PERC, IBC and current HJT; AMPERE performance assessment in terms of LCOE is presented in figure1.

Fig.1 . AMPERE demo pilot line performance assessment in terms of LCOE

Key aspects for European PV market, to compete with mainstream providers, pass through fundamental steps that embrace technological and marketing aspects, such as:

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- ✓ Improve performances without affecting the process complexity to maintain the CAPEX at a limited level
- ✓ Improve reliability towards 40 years lifetime for better LCOE
- ✓ Use of abundant, non-toxic materials
- ✓ Recyclable and low footprint technology
- ✓ Increase market need for the technology

Among the existing solar cells technologies, HJT has demonstrated a large potential to address these challenges. Furthermore, the HJT solar module can be fabricated in a bi-facial architecture, further enhancing the electricity production capacity by at least 20% and opening up many market segments[1]. A first breakdown of costs and a draft of industrial plan has been analyzed and settled. It comes especially from the high level of automation and process control inside the innovation transfer that allow a global cost reduction around 30%. Table 1 summarize cost reduction efforts within AMPERE in the entire PV value chain.

	Ambition within AMPERE	Cost reduction reached at the end of the project (2019)	Cost reduction needed for a constant margin (2020)
At wafer level	Thinner wafers	~25%	30%
At cell level	<ul style="list-style-type: none">· Lower Silver content· Cheaper TCO· Use of Cu for metallization	~40%	30%
At module level	<ul style="list-style-type: none">· Replace Indium in wires· Develop 72 cells· Develop half cells	~30%	30%
At process level	Lower CAPEX for production (PVD, PECVD) of cells and SWCT (module)	~20%	30%
Global reduction	-	~30%	30%

Table 1. *estimated cost reduction due to the innovations transferred during AMPERE*

Conclusions

A premium technology with high efficiency, high reliability, low temperature coefficient and consequently low LCOE will be industrialized in Europe, through the Ampere project. Premium segment is a very attractive option for utility scale PV market segments as it translates directly into very low LCOE. For such market segments, bifacial solar cells increase the annual generation of energy. The advantages in terms of energy gain can be even improved by using HJT technology, due to lower thermal budget and expected lower degradation rate. The project will provide investment pathways for the exploitation of the results to support the GW facilities of the next 5-10 years.

[1] International Technology Roadmap for Photovoltaic (ITRPV): results 2015. Seventh edition: march 2016

[2] **S. De Wolf , A. Descoeurdes, Z. C. Holman, C. Ballif**, High-efficiency Silicon Heterojunction Solar Cells: A Review, Green, Volume 2, Issue 1, Pages 7–24, 2012

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[3] <http://www.meyerburger.com/en/products-systems/industries/photovoltaics/>

[4] <http://www.3sun.com/>

[5] Global Market Outlook , Solar Power / 2015 – 2019, www.solarpowereurope.org.

[6] A. Louwen, A cost roadmap for silicon heterojunction solar cells, Solar Energy Materials & Solar Cells, 147 (2016) 295.